

ISic3071

I.Sicily inscription 3071

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 14468

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 10 cm

Width 29 cm

Depth 3.6 cm

Layout

letters show traces of paint

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 25 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κίτε
2. Ὑπομονή, ἢ μα
3. καρία χρηστιανή

Apparatus

Text of Griesheimer 1989

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645423

PHI 331994

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 39.1023

Griesheimer, M. 1989. Quelques inscriptions chrétiennes de Sicile orientale. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 65: 143-177. At 145 no.2 fig.2

Ferrua, A 1940. Nuovi studi nelle catacombe di Siracusa. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 17: 43-81. At 71

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3071. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357132>